

PLASMA POLYMERIZATION OF BASALT FIBER/POLYLACTIC ACID COMPOSITES: EFFECTS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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1 Introduction

Green composites are being developed to provide more environmentally friendly, economically sound structural and functional materials. The use of bioplastics matrices and natural fiber reinforcements is a way towards that goal. Polylactid acid (PLA), with its plant origin and biodegradable nature, has ecofriendly image and fair physical properties to be the bio-based thermoplastic matrix of choice. As for the matrix, basalt fiber (BF) has the potential for having high strength and superior high temperature performance, in addition to being inert and having natural notion for being made entirely of volcanic rock.

Compatibility should be addressed when mixing inorganic BF and organic PLA since it is determinant to their composites' performance. This study utilizes atmospheric glow discharge (AGD) plasma for surface modification on basalt fiber through plasma polymerization. Glow is generated at atmospheric pressure at or near ambient temperature. Typically, the system operates at high frequency (above 1 kHz) and uses inert gas (argon or helium) as diluent to generate a homogeneous glow discharge through a Penning ionization mechanism [1]. The AGD plasma is considerably uniform, making it suitable for surface treatment processes [1]. The system enables continuous process without the needs for vacuum system, an advantage in terms of cost and practicality. Effect of plasma time to the composite's mechanical properties is the object of interest.

2 Experimental

PLA films used were procured from Green Chemical Co., Ltd., Korea. Woven fabric of basalt fiber (diameter range of 8-12 μm) was from YJC Co., Ltd., Korea. The acrylic acid monomer used was of

reagent grade, procured from Junsei Chemicals, Korea.

The in house AGD plasma system (Fig. 1) used 3kV AC power supply and radio frequency source at 20 kHz. Acrylic acid monomer was used as the precursor, with helium as the carrier gas. The system's setting corresponds to prior experience [1] where plasma polymer of acrylic acid can adhere on other types of fibers for reinforcing PLA matrix. The basalt fiber was exposed to AGD plasma for 0.5, 1.5, 3, 4.5, and 6 minutes.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the atmospheric glow discharge plasma system [2]

PLA films and plasma polymerized BF were hot pressed to produce composites with 25 wt% BF content. For comparison, neat PLA and untreated BF/PLA composite (control) were also produced. Tensile test were conducted on the composites according to ASTM D3039 using Instron 5882 under controlled atmosphere environment. The setting for cross head speed was 5 mm/min. Selected samples were further characterized. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was conducted on the BF using Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS10 with KBr/Ge beam splitter. The FTIR spectra were

recorded from 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} with 2 cm^{-1} resolution, averaged over 32 scans. Thermal analysis on selected samples was performed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a Perkin-Elmer DSC 7 set to scan from 20 to 180°C at the heating rate of 10°C/min under nitrogen atmosphere. The observed output was melting temperature (T_m), heat of fusion (ΔH_f), and crystallinity of PLA and its composites. For morphology analysis, scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM 5800 was used.

3 Results and Discussion

Strength and stiffness of neat PLA and BF/PLA composites are displayed in Fig. 2. It is notable that untreated BF readily exhibits reinforcement effect to the composite. Short period of plasma polymerization on basalt fiber causes reduced strength and stiffness on the composites. Improvement, compared to untreated BF/PLA composite, was shown by composites whose BF was plasma polymerized for at least 3 minutes at the particular setting. The elongation at break of plasma polymerized BF/PLA composite also showed similar trend of decline for exposure time of up to 1.5 minutes and rebound afterwards. This decline on mechanical properties when BF was insufficiently exposed to AGD plasma was not unprecedented. Similar finding was reported on glass fiber/polyester composite where untreated glass fiber composite outperformed plasma polymerized glass fiber composite [3]. This study adds that prolonging plasma exposure time may help in getting the expected reinforcement effect.

AGD plasma polymerized BF surface (Fig. 3) showed smoother appearance than BF as is. Untreated BF readily contains size, applied by the manufacturer to assist its processing and to improve its compatibility with specific matrix to promote strength, stiffness, and durability [4]. The size apparently suits fairly well with the PLA matrix. The distribution of size throughout fiber surface seems uneven, with large portion is uncovered while some sites are overly applied. This uneven distribution seems common due to the high speed nature of fiber processing [4,5]. The longer the plasma polymerization occurred, the smoother the BF surface resulted.

The polymerization within the glow involved metastable helium radicals (Penning reaction). This reaction involves various reactive species, making it random in nature, and often forms polymers without specific repeating unit. So, the macromolecules formed from the acrylic acid precursor are designated as plasma polymer acrylic acid (ppAA).

Fig. 2. Strength and stiffness of BF/PLA composites (X is neat PLA)

Fig. 3. Morphology of BF surface as received (a) and plasma polymerized for 0.5 minute (b), 1.5 minutes (c), and 4.5 minutes (d).

The presence of ppAA on BF surface was detected by FTIR through comparison with the spectrum of as received BF (Table 1). There was shift in C=O

peak which represents the grafted acrylic acid [6]. In addition, there were also shifts in Si—O and C—O peaks, which are related to the silane based sized. The helium used within the glow has high metastable energies ($2^3S = 19.8$ eV and $2^1S = 20.7$ eV) [7]. It was capable of dissociating C=C bond to form ppAA. It also was high enough to dissociate Si—O, Si—C, as well as C—O bonds within the size.

Table 1. FTIR bands of basalt fibers*.

Basalt fiber type	$V_{C=O}$	V_{C-O}	V_{Si-O}
As received	1774	1294	889
Plasma polymerized, 0.5 min	1773	1290	909
Plasma polymerized, 1.5 min	1769	1295	918
Plasma polymerized, 4.5 min	1768	1247	898

*) All units in cm^{-1}

DSC analysis on the composites revealed that plasma polymerized BF/PLA composites, including the optimum one, were less crystalline than untreated BF/PLA composite (Table 2). Although less crystallinity often means worse mechanical properties, the improved adhesion between ppAA interphase and PLA seems offsetting it. This implies that mechanical properties of the composites were dominantly affected by the state of ppAA as the interphase between BF and PLA matrix.

Table 2. Thermal properties of BF/PLA composites.

Sample	T_m	$\Delta H_f^{a)}$	Crystallinity ^{b)}
	(°C)	J/g	%
PLA	113.5	21.13	24.3
Control	114.3	18.35	28.1
Plasma polymerized, 0.5 min	112.8	14.26	21.9
Plasma polymerized, 1.5 min	112.7	13.93	21.3
Plasma polymerized, 4.5 min	113.0	11.00	16.9

^{a)} Per gram of total sample

^{b)} Based on unit mass of PLA component. ΔH_f of PLA crystal = 87 J/g

It was likely that during early period of plasma polymerization, deactivation of the silane based size by plasma polymer acrylic acid (ppAA) occurred while the amount of ppAA itself was not yet sufficient to make considerable adhesion with PLA. Possible mechanisms within the glow were the breakage of organofunctional group of the silane molecules or attachment of acrylic acid oligomers on silane molecules. Only after significant amount of

ppAA was formed on the silane molecules (or whatever was left out of them) on BF surface then adhesion force between ppAA and PLA molecules became apparent in the bulk composite.

As ppAA grows, interphase adhesion with PLA improves, reflected through better strength and stiffness. Possibly, this situation was also complemented by redistribution of excessive silane to more BF surface area. Up to some point, the ppAA-PLA adhesion improvement reaches saturation; in this case it is after 4.5 minutes of plasma polymerization. Steric hindrance might be the cause.

Further observation on the composite's cross section reveals gaps existed between matrix and plasma polymerized BF (Fig. 4), although it was in better condition than that of untreated BF/PLA composites. The indication is that the bond between ppAA interphase and PLA matrix was physical in nature, through hydrogen bonding or van der Waals interaction.

Fig. 4. Cross section image of plasma polymerized BF/PLA composite.

This study shows that AGD plasma is capable of performing surface modification on BF through growing ppAA, affecting the corresponding composite's mechanical properties. Further characterization is recommended to get better insight on the possible plasma polymerization mechanisms by the AGD plasma. Future work will be performed on finding better way to get immediate mechanical properties improvements of the AGD plasma treated BF/PLA composites, including by parameter optimization and alternative monomer precursors.

4 Conclusions

Plasma exposure time on BF affected mechanical properties of its BF/PLA composite. At optimum condition (4.5 minutes of exposure), strength and stiffness increased 45% and 18%, respectively, compared to control. Trend of initial strength and stiffness decline followed by increase beyond 1.5 minutes of plasma exposure was due to the plasma polymerization was reacted on sized (silane based) basalt fiber.

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